

STRESS-STRAINED STATE OF FIBROUS COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The paper discusses a stress-strained state of a unidirectional structure of fibrous composite materials and the suggestion is made of classification of composite residual stresses.

INTRODUCTION

A stress-strained state of fibrous composite materials seems to be a more complex problem than it has been considered earlier in the literature devoted to this phenomenon. First of all it is necessary to note that at their initial condition boron, silicium carbide, steel and other kinds of reinforcing fibers have a high level of residual stresses of the order of 1500 MPa. Boron fibers are characterized by the presence of axial tensile stresses in a center of a fiber and compression stresses at its periphery [1]. As regards a steel wire the picture observed is quite opposite [2]. In the process of a composite material fabrication a fiber stress state is changed under the action of the temperature conditions and new stress fields are developed due to a difference in thermal expansion coefficients of fiber and matrix materials. At a microlevel the fields of thermal, strain and phase residual stresses which exist at a fiber-matrix interface are observed in an entire volume of a composite material at the temperatures different from those of a composite fabrication [3, 4]. At a macrolevel when lamellar fibrous materials are reinforced at different angles the residual stresses existing in them achieve high values [5] due to anisotropy of both elastic moduli and coefficients of linear expansion.

The technological residual stresses should be also considered to be residual macrostresses. They are associated with controlling a force of a fiber bundle tension during a composite fabrication by a winding [6] and a creation of a temperature field inhomogeneity [7]. Stress fields caused by a difference in thermal expansion coefficients of fiber and matrix materials result in a change of an aluminium matrix substructure [8] and a high level of a matrix dislocation density [9]. When fabricating composites with an epoxy matrix [7] the technological stress fields lead to a continuity disturbance and bending the reinforcing elements due to a loss of their plastic stability. Therefore, composite residual stresses still belong to the problems which require a rigorous investigation.

In this work when using the abovementioned terms a field of residual stresses existing in fibers which have opposite signs and are counterbalanced should be added to already known fields of residual microstresses. In contrast to this in [5] it is stated that at a microlevel there are no residual stresses in unidirectional materials. In the latter statement the assumption that fiber and matrix stresses are in balance according to an additivity rule is taken as an axiom. As a

consequence the field of residual stresses suggested here for discussion has not been found earlier using the method of a single matrix fiber, a model of a coaxial cylinder and some other models associated with an averaging of composite characteristics [10,11].

With accumulation of experimental data on stress-strained state of composite materials it became evident that they could not be explained in terms of the notions developed for isotropic materials [12]. In the classification suggested by N. N. Davidenkov [13] the residual stresses of isotropic materials are subdivided into three categories. The first category includes the stresses occurring within the regions the dimensions of which are of the same order as those of a body. They are in balance with each other. When the stresses occur within the volumes which are of the same order as grain sizes and are in balance they belong to the second category. The stresses characteristic of the third category are observed within the volumes which are of the same order as elementary crystal cells and are in balance. This classification can't be used for assessing the residual stresses of fibrous composite materials because of the way they manifest themselves and distributed in these materials. In this connection is probably advantageous to introduce a new classification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On the basis of the investigations conducted the authors consider it reasonable to differentiate three types of residual stresses which are observed in composite materials. Type I residual stresses are those which are developed in fiber and matrix materials during a composite fabrication only due to a difference in the values of thermal expansion coefficients. The fiber stresses are counterbalanced by those of a matrix and distributed over the entire body volume. If an effect of residual stresses on an axial strain is neglected the value of the residual stresses can be defined as [14]:

$$\sigma'_m = (\alpha_m - \alpha_f) \Delta T E_m E_f V_f / E_c, \quad \sigma'_f = \sigma'_m (1 - V_f) / V_f. \quad (1)$$

Here σ'_m and σ'_f are the fiber and matrix residual stresses; α_m and α_f the coefficients of thermal expansion; E_m, E_f and E_c the elasticity moduli of a matrix, fibers and a composite, respectively. In all the cases the maximum value of residual stresses cannot be higher than the matrix yield strength (σ_{mys}), i. e. the condition ($\sigma_m \leq \sigma_{mys}$) is observed. On assumption that the composite yield strength (σ_{cys}) is the stress at which a matrix plastic strain starts under the action of a tension it can be determined as:

$$\sigma_{cys} = \sigma_{mys} (1 - n)(1 - V_f + V_f E_f / E_m). \quad (2)$$

Here $1 \geq \sigma'_m / \sigma_{mys} = n \geq -1$. From (2) it follows that residual stresses can change the value of a yield strength by $\pm 100\%$. The experiments have shown that n is within the range ± 0.6 to 0.8 . This is conditional upon a stresses relaxation. If it is assumed that a plastic matrix has no effect on a fiber breaking strain (ε_f^*) it is valid that:

$$\varepsilon_f^* = \varepsilon'_f + \varepsilon_f = \text{const.} \quad (3)$$

So the strain of fibers at an instant of breaking is equal to the sum of a residual strain and that which is developed under the action of a load (ε_f). As $\varepsilon_c^* = \varepsilon_f$ from (1) and (3) we find that:

$$\varepsilon_c^* = \varepsilon_f - \varepsilon_f' = \varepsilon_f^* + n\sigma_{mys}(1-V_f)/E_fV_f. \quad (4)$$

It can be shown that fiber and matrix strength properties may be reproduced in a composite if:

$$\varepsilon_f^* \geq \sigma_{mys}(1-V_f)/E_fV_f + 2\sigma_{mys}/E_m. \quad (5)$$

As it is shown in [15] the real ultimate strength values of aluminium-steel composite are quite coincident with those calculated using a mixing rule but they are decreased by almost 40 % for composites with brittle fibers. This should not be attributed to type I residual stresses.

A thermal expansion is also affected by residual stresses [16]. On the basis of a strained matrix state the process of a composite heating can be divided into three stages. The matrix is subjected to an elastic strain during the first stage and a material temperature expansion can be calculated according to a mixing rule:

$$\varepsilon_c^t = \frac{\Delta T [\alpha_f V_f E_f + \alpha_m E_m (1-V_f)]}{E_f V_f + E_m (1-V_f)}. \quad (6)$$

At the second stage the sum of residual and thermal stresses achieves the matrix yield strength and a thermal body expansion is accompanied by a plastic matrix strain. In this case depending on a sign and the value of residual stresses the thermal expansion of composites is equal to:

$$\varepsilon_c^t = \Delta T \alpha_f - \sigma_{mys}'(1-V_f)/E_fV_f + n\sigma_{mys}(1-V_f)/E_fV_f. \quad (7)$$

where σ_{mys}' is the matrix yield strength at a given temperature. At the third stage the matrix yield strength tends to zero and as a consequence thermal stresses also tend zero. Then:

$$\varepsilon_c^t = \Delta T \alpha_f + n\sigma_{mys}(1-V_f)/E_fV_f. \quad (8)$$

From the equations (2), (4), (7) and (8) it follows that compressive residual stresses existing in a matrix (tensile stresses in fibers) increase the yield strength and decrease the breaking strain and a thermal expansion coefficient of a composite. The value and sign of type I residual stresses can be changed by a mechanical working (such as rolling, tension, compression, etc.) or a heat treatment of a composite [12,17]. The values of residual stresses can be determined by analytical [4,5] and experimental X-ray methods [4] using diagrams of repeated and alternating modes of loading [1], dilatometric diagrams [18] as well as measuring a length of a specimen and that of a fiber extracted from a specimen after its etching.

The stresses which are developed in separate volumes of a body during a composite fabrication and are in balance are assigned to type II residual stresses. For example, sheets produced by rolling along fibers have a heavy buckling which can be caused by a nonuniform billet expansion. This results in that the fibers arranged over sheet edges are elongated and those in its center are contracted. The buckling of sheets which occurs during a hot pressing results from the presence of a temperature gradient over the surface of heating plates. The presence of type II residual stresses is characteristic of boron-aluminium rods fabricated by a continuous casting. The solidification of a casting is accompanied by a temperature drop which leads to the development

of tensile residual stresses in a central part of a casting and compressive residual stresses on its external surface [19]. When composites are fabricated by a continuous casting there also occurs a temperature drop ΔT across a casting section [20]. Unlike isotropic materials the residual stresses of which are developed due to a plastic strain of a central casting part the composite fibers are only subjected to elastic strains. In this case the development of type II residual stresses can be explained in the following way. A casting produced by a continuous process always would have such a section in which a central part is liquid and the temperature of a surface layer would be lower than that of a crystallization by the value, ΔT . By this is meant that the fibers located in different sites across a casting section would have various values of a thermal expansion. The possibility of a mutual shear of fibers is eliminated in a solidified matrix due to comparatively high casting rates. Therefore, a maximum difference in the values of fiber temperature strains which is observed during a matrix solidification is retained up to a room temperature and is $\Delta T\alpha_f$. Hence, at a room temperature external fibers would be compressed by the value $\Delta T\alpha_f/2$ and internal fibers would be extended by the same value. However, fibers are additionally strained owing to type I residual stresses. Considering this a residual strain of external fibers (ϵ'_{ext}) is:

$$\epsilon'_{ext} = \Delta T\alpha_f/2 + \sigma_{mys}(1-V_f)/E_fV_f. \tag{9}$$

and that of central fibers (ϵ'_{int}) is:

$$\epsilon'_{int} = \Delta T\alpha_f/2 - \sigma_{mys}(1-V_f)/E_fV_f. \tag{10}$$

In contrast to type I residual stresses the type II residual stresses decrease an composite ultimate strength by the value $\Delta\sigma_{cus}$:

$$\Delta\sigma_{cus} = \Delta T\alpha_f E_f V_f / 2. \tag{11}$$

This can be easily understood from a schematic tension diagram of fibers and composite (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Tension diagram of composite

In order to perform experimental investigations of type II residual stresses the composite rods 4 mm and 6 mm in diameter were prepared on the base of Al - 12 % Si alloy containing 70 % of boron fibers 172 μ m in diameter. The specimens of 120.56 mm length were cut out of rods using an electric discharge machine. This eliminated crushing the fibers at specimen ends. The fibers were etched away from the specimens one layer at a time under the action of alkali with subsequent measuring the fiber lengths. The measurement was carried out using a microscope with $\pm 1 \mu$ m precision. The maximum fiber elongation and contraction values of a 4 -mm dia.

specimen were 127 μm , and 75 μm , respectively. The expected decrease of the composite ultimate strength is 244 MPa according to the equation (11).

Fig 2 shows a distribution of residual strain of boron fibers after their etching away one layer at a time across a section of a rod 6 mm in diameter. When rods were subjected to a tensile test their ultimate strength was decreased almost twice from 1700 MPa to 900 MPa with increasing their diameters from 1 mm to 6 mm. This phenomenon does not result only from an increase of an absolute fiber number and consequently the quantity of faults caused by these fibers but the reason is also in the effect of type II residual stresses. Thus, the residual stresses which are developed in separate body volumes and are in balance are associated with the presence of some variable factor in a technological process of a composite fabrication. Type II residual stresses decrease the composite ultimate strengths and the sum of their absolute values cannot be decreased by any thermal or mechanical processing. The level of type II residual stresses can be controlled by varying the parameters of a composite fabrication [21].

The type III residual stresses are those which occur in local body volumes and are in balance. These stresses are caused by a repeated bending of fibers during a composite fabrication using a welding, an explosion as well as boron-aluminium strips in which stresses are developed in the sites where are droplet particles.

Figure 2. Strain distribution of boron fiber after etching

The size of these particles is considerably higher than that of a major part of deposited articles. In these regions fibers are subjected to bending with a tension. This inevitably should lead to a decrease of a composite strength and though the possibility of developing such stresses is beyond question the experimental determination of their numerical values still seems to be scarcely probable.

CONCLUSION

The classification of residual stresses occurring in fibrous composite materials suggested in this paper makes it possible to differently highlight the processes which proceed during a composite fabrication and if need arises to take into account that type II and III residual stresses are rather undesirable factors because they decrease a strength of materials and actually cannot be removed by any subsequent processing.

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